

Observing, Monitoring and Analysing the Economy of Music in Europe with the Digital Music Observatory

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Abstract

The *Feasibility study for the establishment of a European Music Observatory* (in short: EMO Feasibility Study)¹ has identified 13 data gaps, and 4 existing but publicly not available data sources.

The Digital Music Observatory has experience with collecting and internationally harmonizing data in 12/13 identified data gaps, with the exceptions of *The impact of the not-for-profit sector on the overall economy of the music sector*, and already has even pan-European and shared data in some areas.

Regarding the 4 identified existing, not available data sources, the Digital Music Observatory maps the metadata of all of these. It can close half of the of the data gaps pending approval from music stakeholder (data owners), and can replicate the other data.

I. Task list

1. Methodology Issues

II. Filling the Data Gaps

1. Employment; 2. Value of EU's music sector; 3. Structure of the market; 4. The impact of the not-forprofit sector on the overall economy of the music sector; 5. Neighbouring rights; 6. Music publishing; 7. Independent music companies; 8. Live music; 9. Export; 10. Music retail or in-store public performance; 11. Financing of the music sector; 12. Live music regulation; 13. Copyright regulations and evolution of copyright regimes.

Furthermore, the *EMO Feasibility Study* mentions existing data sources that are collected by various organizations, such as GESAC, CISAC and IFPI.

II. The Economy of Music Pillar of the Digital Music Observatory

1. From CEEMID to the Digital Music Observatory *This can be used in excellence / Objectives and WP Implementation.*

2. Cultural and Music Policy Relevance *This can be used as state-of the art in Objectives.*

3. Open Collaboration, Open Policy Analysis, and Open Data *This overlaps with our general WP Implementation.*

III. References

The goals of the Diversity and Circulation Pillar greatly overlap with some aspects of the Economy of Music Pillar.

Cultural diversity policy goals, which want to ensure that the music scene of a country, region or city gets proper exposure on the local media and stages, or less popular genres still find a way to their audiences, go

¹Feasibility study for the establishment of a European Music Observatory (European Commission et al. 2020).

hand in hand with some competition policy and consumer protection targets, and they also align well with the objectives of intellectual property and copyright policies. Because almost all income of artists is connected to the use of music, a lack of diversity, and less opportunities for small-language repertoires, classical or jazz music, also lead to inadequate income connected to their composers, performers and a devaluation of their copyrights and neighboring rights. An excessive concentration of volume of use, and therefore revenues/market share for certain nations, or large publishers/labels is conflicting with competition policy goals.

The 8 years of research and policy use history of the Digital Music Observatory (formerly CEEMID) is connected both to competition law-based cases and cultural policy use cases, using the same data, and an overlapping methodology.

In the 21st century, about 60% of the recorded music sales are made by streaming and user-uploaded content platforms where it is mainly not human curators but AI algorithms that match the vast supply of content to users. These AI algorithms use machine learning from the available biographical, musicological, natural language processed lyrics and review information, the artists music history and the user interaction history, user demographics, and other complex, interrelated information. Our experience shows that a strong presence on global streaming and UUG platform requires a very sophisticated data infrastructure and data knowledge that is not present in smaller, independent music businesses, and not even in small-country national organizations.

The data of the Digital Music Observatory is used – outside the scope of this proposal – in trustworthy AI research when we try to assign blame for the less-than-optimal outcome for small business and small country repertoires for copyright data and metadata problems. These problems related to a larger problem that we work in both Music Economy and Music Diversity and Circulation Pillars. Indirectly, because copyright data management/metadata management problems are among the causes of *Music export, Structure of the market, Value of EU's music sector, Employment, Independent music, Neighbouring rights* problems and data gaps of the *Economy of Music Pillar*, not only that of the Diversity & Circulation problems. Indirectly, because researching these problems requires the same data sources, the same data processing about music present in broadcast, retransmission, streaming and other non-mechanical channels of distribution.

In other words, the Economy of Music Pillar relies on very similar data like the Diversity and Circulation Pillar², but it uses the data in different analytical models. As a joint research project of IViR, Reprex, and other partners found, "... costs can also be understood in a broader sense. Instead of confining the analysis to monetary aspects, it is important to consider broader cultural repercussions, in particular the impact of standardised data formats and comprehensive copyright data systems on cultural diversity, recognition and attribution (in the sense of the moral rights enjoying protection under international copyright law and the national copyright systems of EU Member States) and the visibility and availability of the full spectrum of European creative works."³.

Please find the authoritative copy of this document (or later versions) on Zenodo. Subjects: Music industry; Valuation

Methodology: Economics of Music

Indicator Design

In our work, we will improve several quantitative methodologies used in music copyright data management and cultural statistics, among others, to produce improved indicators for business, policy, and academic use. Throughout the project, we will follow the Eurostat guidelines on creating new indicators (Eurostat 2014, 2018; Angelova-Tosheva and Müller 2019), which will ensure broad consensus-forming among stakeholders around the objectives and methodology of the improved measurements.

²Measuring and Monitoring the Diversity Circulation of European Music with Open Source Technology and Data Sharing Within the Digital Music Observatory(Antal and Molina 2022).

³Ensuring the Visibility and Accessibility of European Creative Content on the World Market - The Need for Copyright Data Improvement in the Light of New Technologies and the Opportunity Arising from Article 17 of the CDSM Directive (Senftleben et al. 2021).

Economic valuation

Our Consortium has extensive experience in using all recognized music valuation methods in practice.⁴ The recognized fair valuation principles stipulated that the “most applicable method” must be used in valuations, which almost always leaves out in copyright contests the (historical) “cost approach,” and leaves open the use of the “income approach” and the “market approach.”

The **income approach** compares the royalty flows of a work of its recording via the using an appropriate “discount rate.” When a user buys in a music store an mp3 file on 1 July 2015, it triggers a single royalty payment after the deductions of the cost of sale on the marketplace. In a streaming platform, the same user’s royalty payments appear every month when she listens to the song, and in radio, usually every year. The discount rate provides a proper comparison between remuneration received in July 2015 and April 2021. The *Discounted cash flow (DCF) models* use the “income approach.” They are not applicable for public performance and zero price platforms, but they are applicable in streaming, provided that we have the correct data. The difficulties are generalization (market participants only see a very small, biased part of the market), and relatively complicated adjustments for accruals and exchange rates. While the earlier CEEMID projects did not find the *hedonic price model* useful valuing recorded music (either on the publishing or the recording side), they may be useful for live music—the hedonic price model can be seen as a version of the “market approach.” We have experience with using the so-called *experimental models* to establish the value of music in stores and restaurants. These models are similar to the hedonic price model, and work with explicitly revealed preferences, they can be formulated as a version of the “market approach” or the “income approach.”

The **market approach** tries to identify a payment rate, regardless of if it is made in lump sum, monthly or annually to established, sufficiently similar uses. Many ideas were tried internationally to identify the sufficiently similar use of music streaming; for example, relating ad-supported and automatically selected songs to radio streams, and relating cases where the user controls the selection of songs, and may even download them to music downloads. We have used in several cases *econometric comparisons* using datasets (available for their members only) by IFPI and CISAC⁵ Our econometric models follow apply both equitable remuneration and fair valuation principles, and similar principles of competition law⁶. Our **market comparators model**, which has been used to for both mechanical and public performance valuations, particularly radio rights, UUG platforms, and private copying. The challenge of valuing music in these contexts, including monitoring the value gap, is the correct estimation of quantities and shadow prices.

The application of *fair valuation principles* is particularly challenging in the case of private copying, where the transactions are not recorded (as they are not market transactions) and in streaming, which is a relatively new technology that is seen in licensing as a mixture of earlier mechanical copy-based and public performance-based licensing, and has so many transactions that most rightsholders (and even their national organizations) like the data processing capacity to administer the rights or challenge incorrect payments.

We will have access to streaming data from a) rightsholders and b) our digital distribution partner, Aload. Furthermore, using the spotifyr software maintained by our Consortium, we will access data from the Spotify Rest API directly. We will use biased, but large data samples, and we will employ advanced statistical, quantitative finance and computer science experience to improve our large, but biased datasets until they become representative.

Economic contributions

We calculate direct, indirect, and induced gross-value added, employment, and tax base effects with our iotables software. The methodological difficulty is working with a linear combination of NAcE 59 and NACE 90 in calculations. For such a combination, we use the music professional surveys and enterprise surveys.

⁴See @ref(#obj-economic-value) and references to (PwC 2008; IFRS 2011; Flignor and Orozco 2006; Puca and Zyla 2019).

⁵CISAC offers very different kind of data, because since the *Commission v CISAC* case (InfoCuria 2013) it refrains from directly helping its members price-setting. CISAC’s key performance indicator is the revenue connected to a certain right, which can be used as a basic of calculating shadow prices.

⁶The jurisprudence of the Court of the European Union, particularly *OSA v Léčebné lázně Mariánské Lázně* (InfoCuria 2014) and *AKKA/LAA vs Konkurences padome* (InfoCuria 2017) must be considered when making market comparisons.

Reconciliation of fair value and equitable remuneration

In our work, we will place a great emphasis to reconcile the legal concepts of intellectual properties, and particularly copyrights and neighboring rights with economics. This is both a scientific and practical necessity, because rightholders are selling rights created by intellectual property and copyright law. These rights are, from an economic point of view, artificial monopolies. As monopolies, they are protected by the TEU and national law, therefore they are not anti-competitive, but their exploitation must abide competition law, too.

Socio-legal scholars, economists, and royalty accountants and finance professionals use the concepts of their professions. *Equitable remuneration* is a legal concept which has an economic aspect. In international law, it was first enshrined as Convention C100 of the ILO, stipulating that men and women should receive equal pay for equal work. This convention is ratified by almost all countries in the world, with the notable exception of the United States. Within the context of international copyright law, it was introduced as a modification of the Berne Convention by the Rome Convention for the remuneration of the broadcasting of recorded fixation of music works (recordings) since 1971. These copyright conventions are administered by the WIPO (WIPO 1996a, 1996b). However, these international treaties do not set an international standard on how to calculate equitable remuneration, and do not apply to all uses of music works and their recordings, and various countries have a large leeway to set such rules.

The actual application of music valuation must not only abide by these rules, but also the accounting (which is harmonized on EU level, and under IFRS), particularly royalty accounting, and the economics of intellectual properties. Our valuation models transcend copyright jurisdiction—the fair value standard, for example, is incorporated in the law of every EU member state. Therefore, our economic indicators as benchmarks, and our valuation techniques will be applicable in all EU countries, but national copyright law (also governing neighboring rights) will certainly limit the practical applicability of our findings. In an international context, a study of Europe Economics and IViR has shown that there are notable differences in how *equitable remuneration* is understood – and it is often used as a synonym to *fair* remuneration (Europe Economics & IVIR 2015). In our understanding, the equitable remuneration should happen at fair value as defined by economics and international accounting standards. In our research output, we will always make sure that we make a sound analysis from statistical, economic, and copyright law perspectives, too.

Enterprise surveys

Enterprise surveying is very challenging, because most music enterprises are microenterprises, and they are exempted from standard statistical data collections (which in Europe usually start with an employee count of at least 10 people, a very rare phenomenon in music.) Cultural microenterprises usually do not have a clear activity profile, and it is very difficult to find out which microenterprises are active in the music industry, and which are not. Our approach in the past 8 years had been the use and perfection of a music professional survey, which is a microenterprise appropriate, personal survey. Making sure that such a survey remains representative is a difficult task.

Copyright management data, metadata

According to the *EMO Feasibility Study*, there is already an existing pool of data that would allow the European Music Observatory to start compiling information about the European music sector. Various potential sources and providers of data are provided in the following section (2.4). Many of these providers have already indicated support for a future European Music Observatory, and are willing to collaborate and provide data. However, some data is not collected or is not aggregated in a way that it can be compared across Europe.⁷

The Digital Music Observatory (formerly CEEMID) has been identified among these data sources. CEEMID, started in 2014 by the representative music stakeholders of 3 EU countries, has been already collecting data in all EU countries in a standardized manner by 2019. Similarly to the Policy Brief of xxxxx, And the Finnish collective management society Teosto, the Hungarian, Slovak, Croatian, Czech, and eventually further

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collective management societies realized that there is a long continuum between public and confidential data, and even confidential data can be shared and published in some form.

In fact, since 2014, the Digital Music Observatory (formerly CEEMID) successfully piloted data collection, standardization and harmonization procedures that can fill all the data gaps identified in the music diversity and circulation pillar of the future European Music Observatory. “Neighbouring rights”: Some data exists via SCAPR and AEPO-ARTIS, but it is not made public. Neighboring rights are not present in the circulation of live music. In recorded music, however, our experience shows that this information can be inferred, because the rights represented by SCAPR and AEPO-ARTIS members cannot be separately licensed from the rights represented by CISAC/GESAC or IFPI members, given that the successful licensing of recording requires some form consent from authors, producers and performers (which may have been already given at the time of the recording.) In fact, we do not see this as an independent data gap, nevertheless, we are inviting SCAPR and AEPO-ARTIS and its members to our open collaboration, because their existing data can be a very useful estimation point.

“Through local societies and GESAC and CISAC, it is possible to draw a picture of the sector on a national and pan-European level. However, the flow of rights that circulate between the various countries through authors’ societies’ reciprocal agreements is not available and could constitute a good indicator of the circulation of repertoire, in line with the Transparency report requested by the Directive 2014/26/EU on collective management of copyright and related rights, which requires to provide information on relationships with other collective management organisations, with a description of at least the following items: amounts received from other collective management organisations and amounts paid to other collective management organisations, with a breakdown per category of rights, per type of use and per organisation.”

“Neighbouring rights”: Some data exists via SCAPR and AEPO-ARTIS, but it is not made public. Neighboring rights are not present in the circulation of live music. In recorded music, however, our experience shows that this information can be inferred, because the rights represented by SCAPR and AEPO-ARTIS members cannot be separately licensed from the rights represented by CISAC/GESAC or IFPI members, given that the successful licensing of recording requires some form consent from authors, producers and performers (which may have been already given at the time of the recording.) In fact, we do not see this as an independent data gap, nevertheless, we are inviting SCAPR and AEPO-ARTIS and its members to our open collaboration, because their existing data can be a very useful estimation point.

Employment

The *EMO Feasibility Study* identifies the “the absence of granularity on the employment of the various sub-sectors, in particular in defining the roles of the various sub-sectors and the importance of the not-for-profit sector in terms of employment.”

MOre text here from the HU and SK music industry reports.

Value of EU’s music sector

The *EMO Feasibility Study* identifies the No aggregated data since EY’s study in 2015

Structure of the market

The *EMO Feasibility Study* identifies this data gap as the “absence of pan-European data detailing the number of companies, employees, revenues for the sector and the subsectors.”

The impact of the not-forprofit sector on the overall economy of the music sector

The *EMO Feasibility Study* identifies this data gap as “no data available on the specific impact of the not-for-profit sector, especially in the live music sub-sector.”

In our work plan, this data gap has the lowest priority.

No aggregated data on neighbouring rights collections

The *EMO Feasibility Study* identifies this data gap as there are “Synchronisation rights IFPI data available on the recorded music side but not on the publishing side, and there is no aggregated data on the music European music publishing business” and suggests partnering with ICMP.

Partner with IFPI and ICMP to come up with a data model to evaluate sync rights in Europe and by country.

Independent music

The *EMO Feasibility Study* identifies this data gap as “no aggregated data on the independent music sector (value, number of companies, employees, etc.)”

Live music

According to the *EMO Feasibility Study* “some data is compiled by Live DMA, ETEP or Yourope, but there is no aggregated data on the pan-European live music sector listing the value of the market, the number and size of venues and shows, number of festivals, share of European artists, among other data points.”

CEEMID has been collecting live music data on both national and pan-European level from 2014.

Export

According to the *EMO Feasibility Study* “no pan-European data on the export flows between EU countries and outside the EU.”

In our view, these data exist, partly in shareable, but currently confidential data sources, and partly in open data, but not processed and publicly not available data sources.

Music retail or in-store public performance

The *EMO Feasibility Study* identifies this data gap as there is “granular data on some countries via retail associations (UK, France, Germany) but no pan-European aggregated data.”

Financing of the music sector

The *EMO Feasibility Study* identifies this data gap as there is “no aggregated data on how the sector is financed (from investment fund to bank loans and subsidies).”

Live music regulation

The *EMO Feasibility Study* identifies this data gap as there is “no aggregated information available on the various legal and tax systems within the EU applied to the live music sector.”

In partnership with live music organisations, export offices, coordinate a report on the various schemes in place, suggest best practices and make recommendations on how to reduce friction between systems.

Copyright regulations and evolution of copyright regimes

The *EMO Feasibility Study* identifies this data gap as there are “many copyright laws applicable in Europe originate from the Commission, there are few instruments available to monitor the state of copyright regulation across the EU. Set up an ad hoc group with stakeholders to determine the scope of the EMO’s research framework in the field and identify a series of themes to be researched by the EMO.”

Joost, I think that this could connect to your existing projects.

The Economy of Music Pillar of the Digital Music Observatory

According to the *EMO Feasibility Study*, "there is already an existing pool of data that would allow the European Music Observatory to start compiling information about the European music sector. Various potential sources and providers of data are ... [available, such as our *Digital Music Observatory*]. Many of these providers have already indicated support for a future European Music Observatory, and are willing to collaborate and provide data. However, some data is not collected or is not aggregated in a way that it can be compared across Europe⁸.

From CEEMID to the Digital Music Observatory

The Digital Music Observatory (formerly CEEMID) has been identified among these data sources⁹. CEEMID was originally an acronym for a data integration project that aimed to *Create a Regional Music Database to Support Professional National Reporting, Economic Valuation and a Regional Music Study*¹⁰. According to the "CEEMID can transfer thousands of indicators that are reproducible and verifiable, open-source software that creates them to a European Music Observatory. In particular, CEEMID provides a useful and interesting approach to harnessing the possibilities of open data in Europe in relation to the music sector, which should be further explored by the European Music Observatory in its start-up phase."¹¹

The Digital Music Observatory is built on the gradual, and open extension of the original CEEMID consortium, and builds on practical research and innovation that contributed to many music policy goals in an increasing number of countries since 2014. The original CEEMID consortium delivered the first Hungarian music industry studies (followed by several subsequent ones), the Slovak national music industry study, *Private Copying in Croatia*, and eventually the regional Central European Music Industry Report.¹² All of these industry studies addressed the problem of shrinking competitiveness in of the small language repertoire in the streaming era.

The Feasibility Study is built on a consensus of many European music organizations "that a European Music Observatory should act as a centralised music data and an intelligence hub at European level." However, as a pilot project and policy brief carried out in Finland¹³, or the CEEMID project in Central and Eastern Europe has shown, has its limits. We believe that the existing data availability is better than that described in the *Feasibility study*, and since the creation of this report, it has only got better.

Since 2014, the Digital Music Observatory (former CEEMID) successfully piloted data collection, standardization and harmonization procedures that can fill all the data gaps identified in the music diversity and circulation pillar of the future European Music Observatory. CEEMID was transformed into a "Demo Music Observatory" on 15 September 2020¹⁴ and eventually named *Digital Music Observatory* in 2021. Its policy relevance was also recognized in the United Kingdom after Brexit¹⁵.

The Digital Music Observatory follows the *Open Policy Analysis Guidelines*¹⁶ The OPA Guidelines give practical guidance on how to improve the transparency, replicability, and as a result, the reusability of the

⁸Feasibility study for the establishment of a European Music Observatory (European Commission et al. 2020, pp31–34).

⁹Our observatory is mentioned to be able to participate with "data collection and integration system based on open data, opensources and online surveys" in all pillars of the future European Music Observatory, including Diversity & Circulation (European Commission et al. 2020, p40.)

¹⁰The original aim of CEEMID was *Measuring and Reporting Regional Economic Value Added, National Income and Employment by the Music Industry in a Creative Industries Perspective* Three national collective management societies and their consultant signed Memorandum of Understanding about this in 2014 (Artisjus et al. 2014).

¹¹Feasibility study for the establishment of a European Music Observatory (European Commission et al. 2020, pp147–148).

¹²A ProArt zeneipari jelentése (Antal 2015) and *The Growth of the Hungarian Popular Music Repertoire: Who Creates It And How Does It Find An Audience* (Antal 2017); *Správa o slovenskom hudobnom priemysle* (Antal 2019b), *Private copying in Croatia* (Antal 2019a), Central European Music Industry Report (Antal 2020).

¹³See the Policy Brief *A Symphony, not a Solo* (Osimo et al. 2019).

¹⁴Antal-Szentirmay: Launching Our Demo Music Observatory (blogpost)

¹⁵Written evidence submitted by The state51 Music Group. Economics of music streaming review. Response to call for evidence (state51 Music Group 2020).

¹⁶The Open Policy Analysis Guidelines which grew out from several initiatives in research transparency, such as the Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences, the Data Access and Research Transparency (DA-RT) group, the Center for Open Science and their TOP Guideline, the Meta-Research Innovation Center at Stanford University (BITSS 2019; Hoces de la Guardia, Grant, and Miguel 2020a).

policy-making work with a scientific underpinning.

The *EMO Feasibility Study* acknowledges the importance of open data. The “EMO should also take advantage of open data where possible. Open data is data that can be freely used, re-used and redistributed by anyone. [...] Using some form of open source software where relevant would allow an EMO to access a continuous peer-review of data ingestion, processing, corrections and indicator creation by statisticians, data scientists and academics.”¹⁷

As stated in this final report, the 2019 Open Data Directive further extended the availability of re-usable public sector information (PSI) with *open science data*. In both PSI, as open government data, and in open science data, there is a huge potential to fill in the data gaps without new data collection—the fact that data can be reused instead of being recollected is the main aim of the directive. However, open data does not mean *public data*. Open data means that taxpayer funded research data can be repurposes, reprocessed, and reused—the Digital Music Observatory is an expert on such data science techniques.

The *Digital Music Observatory is not an alternative to the future European Music Observatory*, just its open source, open data driven voluntary, based on open collaboration with music industry stakeholders, music policy makers and users, academic researchers, individual and citizen scientists, and individual artists. Because we create fully automated research tools that are creating open datasets, and open source software, even our research infrastructure can be fully transferred to a future European Music Observatory¹⁸.

We are not planning to make a competing data observatory. We want to provide a minimum viable model of creating at least a hundred useful indicators—selected from hundreds of indicator-candidates with user feedback—that goes through the unit-testing of data science and computer science, the peer-review of open-source scientific algorithm/software development, the methodological peer-review of science, and eventually user verification from music industry users. This will make sure that the indicators can be reproduced, refreshed, and placed in a future European Music Observatory with at least as good data quality as one would expect from a governmental statistical source or Eurostat.

The aim of the Digital Music Observatory is to maximize transparency by introducing to the policy context of Music Moves Europe, and the wider European music ecosystem the Open Policy Analysis framework. (See Open Collaboration, Open Policy Analysis, and Open Data.)

Open Collaboration, Open Policy Analysis, and Open Data

We aim to maximize transparency by introducing to the policy context of Music Moves Europe, and the wider European music ecosystem the Open Policy Analysis framework. (BITSS 2019; Hoces de la Guardia, Grant, and Miguel 2020b).

Our policy tools will make possible the first, large scale European application of the Open Policy Analysis, which grew out from several initiatives in research transparency, such as the Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences, the Data Access and Research Transparency (DA-RT) group, the Center for Open Science and their TOP Guideline, the Meta-Research Innovation Center at Stanford University. Globally, the World Bank promotes this framework (Hoces de la Guardia, Grant, and Miguel 2020b; Berkeley Initiative for Transparency in the Social Sciences et al. 2020) and they are fully in line with the Open Science objectives of the European Union (Commission et al. 2020).

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knitr::include_graphics(file.path("plots", "OPA_main_figure_with_source.png"))
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We believe that existing data availability is better than that described in the *Feasibility study*. As stated in this final report, the 2019 Open Data Directive further extended the availability of re-usable public sector information (PSI) with open science data. In both PSI, as open government data, and in open science data,

¹⁷In the EU, open data is governed by Directive (EU) 2019/1024 on open data and the re-use of public sector information (EUR-Lex 2019), which replaced the Public Sector Information Directive, also known as the ‘PSI Directive’ which dated from 2003 and was subsequently amended in 2013. Feasibility study for the establishment of a European Music Observatory (European Commission et al. 2020, p38).

¹⁸In other words, our aim, fully in line with the intentions of the Commission expert who were encouraging us to make this proposal, and with the Feasibility Study, is to create open source scientific/statistical software and pilot open data that can be utilized in 4/4 identified data gaps related to music diversity and circulation in the European Music Observatory.

Source: <https://www.bitss.org/opa/>

Figure 1: Our ambition to increase transparency with introducing the Open Policy Analysis into the European music policies and collaborative data use in the European industry.

there is a huge potential to fill in the data gaps without new data collection—the fact that data can be reused instead of being recollected is the main aim of the directive. These open data sources are legally open but are not accessible without further investment, and our Consortium wants to make this investment, and produce about 50% of all the data needs of the future European Music Observatory.

It also mentioned the work CEEMID, a bottom-up initiative originally started by three collective management societies, and eventually joined by more than 60 stakeholders in 12 European countries to fill in some of these gaps with a) voluntary data integration among partners b) open data re-processing c) co-financed data collection. Our proposal wants to put the former CEEMID, currently named Digital Music Observatory, a more solid scientific and methodological foundation, to make it more user-friendly, and to exploit state-of-art statistical, data science and computer science methods to provide more comprehensive, timely, and accurate services for the European music sector.

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